

Book of abstracts

TipESM ClimTip conference

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11 Rue Pierre et Marie Curie, 75005 Paris.

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Session 1: Cryosphere

The ice sheets of Greenland and Antarctica are widely recognised as major tipping elements of the Earth System, with the potential for global impact through millennial-scale commitments to sea level rise. In addition, ice mass loss can impact the global ocean circulation, which may trigger tipping of other tipping elements. In this session we will discuss how the response of these ice sheets to climate change is currently being modelled, and how to deal with the considerable uncertainty in their past history, relevant physical mechanisms and likelihood of future abrupt and irreversible change.

Keynote talk: The reversibility of ice sheet and sea level responses at different global warming levels in a state of the art Earth System Model

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Robin Smith

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Submission date: 7 March 2025

Abstract: Much of the literature around tipping points is based on simplified models and statistical analyses, which limits our ability to understand tipping interactions between multiple components in the real Earth System. In particular, a variety of positive feedbacks in the climate system and ice sheets have been proposed that could lead to greatly increased rates of ice sheet mass loss and irreversible sea level rise if triggered. We have conducted a large ensemble of simulations with UKESM, a highly complex, CMIP-class Earth System Model in a framework designed to investigate a broad spectrum of process-based component interactions and systematically test for thresholds beyond which significant changes in the sensitivity or reversibility of key Earth System processes occurs. UKESM includes a sophisticated, process-based, two-way coupling between the climate system and dynamic models of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. Focusing on transient responses and the reversibility of forced changes on policy-relevant timescales, we describe the changes simulated in polar climate and the components of ice sheet mass balance at different global warming levels, along with the associated rates of sea level rise.

Presentation 1: Antarctica's inner values – tapping Antarctica's sub-surface to project its future evolution

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Johannes Sutter

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Submission date: 28 March 2025

Abstract: The evolution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) during the coming centuries is highly uncertain. Its future path could make it the dominating driver of global sea level rise, thwarting even a complete loss of the entire Greenland Ice Sheet under the most dire climate scenarios. Currently, model studies do not agree on the ice sheet's future trajectory

and in part even suggest opposing sea level contributions which limits the usefulness of such projections. Here, we outline a promising approach to reduce some uncertainties pertaining to ice sheet model parameterizations and initializations by tapping the rich resource of the internal stratigraphic scaffold which makes up the Antarctic Ice Sheet. We present how these isochrones can be used to assess past and future ice sheet stability, climatic conditions and the parametric uncertainties plaguing current modelling efforts.

Presentation 2: The fates of the Greenland ice sheet under the idealised scenarios of the TIPMIP-ESM protocol as simulated by EC-Earth3-ESM

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Jorge Bernales

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Submission date: 10 March 2025

Authors: Jorge Bernales, Chuncheng Guo, Shuting Yang

Abstract: Following the TIPMIP-ESM experiment protocol, we simulate a set of idealised emission-driven overshoot scenarios using the post-CMIP6 version of the EC-Earth3 Earth system model, which includes an interactive Greenland ice sheet. These simulations consist of: 1) ramp-up runs with a constant CO₂ emission rate that drives global mean surface air temperature warming at a rate of 0.2 K/decade; 2) stabilisation runs that span >300 years under zero CO₂ emission branched out from the ramp-up runs at multiple global warming levels; and 3) ramp-down runs (branched after 50 years' stabilisation runs) that bring the climate back to pre-industrial levels at the same but negative CO₂ emission rate as the ramp-up.

We present and discuss the simulated responses of the Greenland ice sheet under our preliminary idealised global simulations, which display features such as a linear decline of the Atlantic meridional ocean circulation during the ramp-up phase followed by a stabilisation phase and an eventual overshoot-type recovery during the ramp-down phase. Among our findings, we observe that the acceleration of surface melting and subsequent mass loss in the Greenland Ice Sheet during the ramp-up phase hardly reverses during the ramp-down phase if a high global warming level is reached.

Presentation 3: The Antarctic response to a 1% Annual Increase in Atmospheric CO₂

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Javier Blasco

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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Authors: Javier Blasco, Britta Grusdt, Marisa Montoya, Jorge Alvarez-Solas and Alexander Robinson

Abstract: The Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) holds the largest potential for global sea-level rise, yet it remains the greatest source of uncertainty in future projections. While the physical processes driving AIS mass loss are well understood, significant uncertainties persist. These stem from gaps in understanding Antarctic-specific processes and the variability in future warming scenarios. From modeling and paleo-climatic studies it is well established that oceanic warming of 1–3°C in the Amundsen Sea Embayment could lead to a collapse of the marine regions of the AIS via the Marine Ice Sheet Instability (MISI) feedback mechanism. Understanding the proximity to this tipping point is crucial for accurate sea-level rise projections and developing effective adaptation strategies. However, the relationship between this threshold and CO₂ emissions remains elusive. To address this, we conducted simulations of the AIS forced by CMIP6 GCMs under a scenario of 1% annual CO₂ increase until 2300. For this, we use an ice-sheet-shelf model ensemble initialized with varying configurations to account for key uncertainties, including ice-ocean interactions, basal friction and climate variability. Additionally, complementary experiments examine the sea-level contributions under global mean temperature increase scenarios of 1.5°C, 2.0°C, and 2.5°C relative to the 1990–2020 historical period.

Session 2: Biosphere incl. Amazon

This session will encompass a variety of aspects related to tipping points in the Biosphere. The main points in discussion are the response of various ecosystems to external forcings, how these affect their resilience and the potential impacts of resilience loss to these ecosystems and society. These debates intend to contribute to the assessment of the likelihood and the risks of approaching or crossing eventual tipping points in the Biosphere.

Keynote talk: Amazon forest decline driven by both climate change and land-use change

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Julia Pongratz

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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Authors: Selma Bultan, Yiannis Moustakis, Sebastian Bathiany, Niklas Boers, Raphael Ganzenmüller, Gergana Gyuleva, Lucas Ferreira Correa, Julia Pongratz

Abstract: The Amazon rainforest, one of the key components of the climate system and hotspot of biodiversity, is progressively degrading through anthropogenic climate and land-use change. The threat of a basin-wide forest collapse under progressive climate change has been studied previously, but a holistic assessment of the individual and combined spatiotemporal impacts of changing climate and especially land-use on the Amazon forest is currently lacking. Here, we use projections from Earth System Models under different climate and land-use pathways to assess the response of the Amazon rainforest to varying degrees of future climate and land-use change. We find that up to 38% of the mid 20th century forest area is projected to disappear by 2100, with 27% due to continued deforestation and 11% due to unmitigated climate change. Consistent across all models, there is an increasing risk of abrupt rather than gradual forest decline with progressing climate change, together with a non-linear intensification of forest decline beyond a global warming level of 2.3°C. These are early indications that the forest is at severe risk of large-scale and potentially irreversible loss, unless actions to stop deforestation and mitigate climate change are taken.

Presentation 1: Bridging Data and Theory for Monitoring Resilience Changes in Tropical Forests

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Lana Blaschke

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Submission date: 11 March 2025

Abstract: Resilience of tropical forests to anthropogenic forcing is crucial for climate change mitigation, and several studies are concerned with quantifying changes thereof. Commonly, they employ estimators of Critical Slowing Down in the advent of a Tipping Point. Yet, the

underlying theory imposes several assumptions about the data, usually remote sensing vegetation products. We develop a framework to validate the assumptions, test which resilience estimators best represent recovery for the given data, and apply it to 16 different vegetation products and several resilience metrics. This will allow us to find optimal combinations of data and resilience estimators, on which we then perform robust resilience analyses.

Presentation 2: Disaster-induced displacement as a potential social tipping element

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Sandra Zimmermann

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Submission date: 28 March 2025

Abstract: In 2023, extreme weather events triggered 26.4 million displacements worldwide, with floods accounting for the largest share. Being displaced can adversely affect an individual's physical and mental health, their livelihood as well as their personal security. The duration of displacement strongly depends on the time required to reconstruct damaged housing and infrastructure. Considering the projected increase in frequency and intensity of flood hazards in most parts of the world, we may observe that the duration of displacement at some point exceeds the return interval of flood hazards, potentially preventing displaced persons from returning. To assess the risk of disaster-induced displacement becoming permanent, we developed a two-step flood displacement risk model. The model integrates multiple flood hazard components with disaster vulnerability indicators in a Bayesian multilevel regression framework to identify regions of displacement risk today as well as under future population and climate scenarios. In combination with the estimated duration of displacement based on the time needed to reconstruct buildings, we plan to investigate recovery times for future simulated displacement events to estimate regions of risk for permanent flood-induced displacement.

Presentation 3: Deep sea and seafloor ecosystem response to net-zero and negative emissions

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Friederike Frøb

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Submission date: 10 March 2025

Abstract: Ongoing ocean warming, deoxygenation, acidification and limited nutrient availability will increase the probability of large regime shifts within marine ecosystems. Deep-sea ecosystems are adapted to the stable ambient conditions and are highly vulnerable to human impacts and climate change. Future projections show considerable heat accumulation at depth, and moreover, in strong overshoot scenarios, irreversibility is found in various properties in the deep ocean. Here, we compare rates of warming, acidification, and deoxygenation at depth and the seafloor for a range of emission driven

idealized overshoot scenarios run with the fully coupled Norwegian Earth System Model version 2 (NorESM2). We discuss the impact that changing ambient conditions have for deep sea ecosystems at the example of *Lophelia Pertusa*, a common cold-water coral found in the North Atlantic. The continued exposure to calcium carbonate undersaturation and inhibited aerobic activity due to warming and deoxygenation lead to physiologically unsustainable conditions for cold water corals, which could be alleviated by sustained food supply, i.e., increased export production. We therefore conclude by showing different potential habitat extents in relation to environmental stressors under different evolving climates.

Session 3: AMOC, SPG and uncertainties of their projections

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) plays a major role in the transport of heat and fresh water around the climate system. It is known to be sensitive to increasing greenhouse gases, and climate models show that it has the potential for abrupt tipping behaviour under some circumstances. On a more regional scale, the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre (SPG) circulation plays an important role in the AMOC and can exhibit more localised tipping. This session discusses potential future evolution of the AMOC and SPG. A particular theme is exploring how limited (and sometimes biased) information from models can be combined with limited available observations, to improve predictions of future behaviour, including early warning of tipping.

Keynote talk: On-going and future changes of the AMOC: what can we learn from combining models and various sources of observations?

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Didier Swingedouw

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Submission date: 10 March 2025

Abstract: While the AMOC will very likely weaken during this century due to the global warming effect, the amplitude of this change and the role of internal variability on this fate is still very uncertain. In this presentation we will explore the potential recent changes of the AMOC in regards to internal variability and the implications it might have in our estimate of future changes. The forced response of the AMOC to global warming will be then assessed using multiple observational constraints. The main results do show a damped weakening of the AMOC until the mid-21st century due to internal variability, while it might accelerate in the second half, with a larger weakening than estimated by the ensemble mean of climate models when constrained by observations.

Presentation 1: AMOC thresholds in CMIP6 models: NAHosMIP

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Laura Jackson

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Submission date: 24 March 2025

Abstract: The Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC) is an important part of our climate system, which keeps the North Atlantic relatively warm. It is predicted to weaken under climate change. The AMOC may have a threshold beyond which recovery is difficult, hence showing quasi-irreversibility (hysteresis). Although hysteresis has been seen in some models, it has been difficult to demonstrate in comprehensive global climate models.

We present results from the North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project (NAHosMIP), where we applied an idealised forcing of a freshwater flux over the North Atlantic in 8 CMIP6 models to explore this threshold. The AMOC weakens in all models from the freshening, but once the freshening ceases, the AMOC recovers in some models, and in others it stays in a weakened state. Those models which reach a state with little deep convection in the North Atlantic are those where the AMOC does not recover. We will discuss mechanisms behind the different behaviour in the different models.

Presentation 2: Reconciled warning signals in observations and models imply approaching AMOC tipping point

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Yechul Shin

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Submission date: 21 March 2025

Abstract: Paleoclimate proxy and models suggest that the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) can transition abruptly between a strong and a weak state. Empirical warning in observational fingerprints raise concerns that the system may be approaching a tipping point. However, it remains unclear whether warning of AMOC tipping are overlooked in ESMs or overinterpreted in observations, calling for investigations of AMOC stability. Here, based on the concept of critical slowing down, AMOC stability decline is identified in the eastern SPNA in both observations and ESMs. The observed signal can be reconciled with the modeled one only under warming exceeding the Paris Agreement goal. Our results suggest that the observed AMOC may indeed be losing stability and thus reach a tipping point earlier than state-of-the-art ESMs suggest.

Presentation 3: Statistically Optimal Fingerprints for the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation and the Sub-Polar Gyre

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Bahar Emirzade

Affiliation: Technical University Munich

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Submission date: 21 March 2025

Abstract: The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) and the Sub-Polar Gyre (SPG) are critical components of the Atlantic Ocean's circulation, playing key roles in regulating regional and global climate.

Identifying accurate fingerprints for these systems is essential for monitoring their stability and detecting early signs of potential tipping points. This thesis evaluates the performance of three statistical models — linear regression, LASSO, and Ridge regression — using sea surface temperature (SST) and sea surface salinity (SSS) data from CMIP6 models to reconstruct AMOC and SPG dynamics. Ridge regression emerges as the most effective method, offering robust and interpretable fingerprints that capture both long-term trends and short-term variability.

Our key finding is that statistically driven Ridge fingerprints outperform traditional SST-based metrics, particularly in distinguishing AMOC from SPG, highlighting the value of advanced statistical approaches for tracking complex ocean processes. Notably, the SPG reconstructions exhibit lower accuracy. These results underscore the potential of machine-learning-based fingerprints to enhance long-term climate monitoring and provide early warnings for AMOC and SPG destabilization. Future work could extend these methods to observational datasets and assess their performance under diverse climate scenarios.

Presentation 4: Critical Salinity as an Early Warning of Tipping Point in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Lucas Almeida
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Submission date: 10 March 2025

Abstract: The North Atlantic subpolar gyre (SPG) plays a crucial role in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) and climate through various teleconnections. This study investigates its potential tipping point using CMIP6 projections from three models: CESM2-WACCM, MRI-ESM2-0, and NorESM2-LM. Results indicate that SPG destabilization is primarily driven by upper-ocean freshening, leading to strong stratification and surface cooling. This stabilizes the water column, reduces mixed layer depth (MLD), and weakens vertical mixing. Using a density-based approach, we identify a critical surface salinity threshold ($\sim 33.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), below which rapid cooling, reduced convection, and potentially irreversible transitions occur. The tipping point is preceded by an expansion of areas where surface salinity falls below this threshold, suggesting its potential use as an early warning signal. These findings highlight the SPG's vulnerability to salinity-driven tipping, emphasizing the need for precise monitoring and improved modeling to enhance climate predictability.

Presentation 5: Collapse of the AMOC in a Strongly Eddyding Ocean-Only Model

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Henk Dijkstra
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Submission date: 16 March 2025

Abstract: A collapse of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) under a quasi-equilibrium freshwater forcing has now been found in a hierarchy of ocean-climate models and up to a fully-coupled climate model, the Community Earth System Model (CESM). However, the effects of eddies on the ocean flows are represented in a highly idealised way in the CESM and it is unknown how these affect AMOC stability. Here, we show results of the first quasi-equilibrium hosing simulation with a strongly eddyding ocean-only model in which the AMOC collapses. By comparing these results to those of a companion non-eddyding simulation with the same model, it is found that eddies are able to

maintain a weak AMOC flow in the collapsed state. In addition, we find that the AMOC induced freshwater transport at 34S is a reliable physics-based early warning indicator for the onset of the AMOC collapse.

Presentation 6: Noise-shaped hysteresis cycles of the AMOC under increasing CO₂ forcing

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Susanna Corti

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Submission date: 6 March 2025

Abstract: The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) stability landscape is commonly investigated with single-realization hysteresis diagrams driven by freshwater input in the North Atlantic Ocean. However, the effect of CO₂ forcing on one side and the role of internal climate variability on the timing of tipping and the AMOC hysteresis on the other side remain less explored. Here, we address this gap by running three independent AMOC hysteresis simulations, consisting of a slow ramp-up plus ramp-down in the CO₂ concentration (0.2 ppm/year) within the PlaSim-Large-Scale Geostrophic (LSG) intermediate complexity model. We show that the realizations of the CO₂-driven hysteresis cycle, and particularly, the timing of the tipping and recovery, are remarkably affected by internal climate variability. In one of the three simulations, we even observe a reversed cycle, where the AMOC recovers at a higher CO₂ level than at the collapse point. While statistical Early Warning Signals (EWSs) show some success in detecting the tipping points, we also find that the internal variability in the EWS considerably reduces the predictability of collapse and leads to false positives of an approaching AMOC tipping. We suggest that the AMOC collapse in the presence of internal climate variability may have characteristics that deviate substantially from the behavior seen in simple models and that caution is needed when interpreting results from a single-experiment realization. Our findings highlight the need for a probabilistic approach in defining a “safe operating space” for AMOC stability, since it might not be possible to define a single critical CO₂ threshold to prevent AMOC collapse.

Session 4: Tipping points prediction methodology

We have seen many studies exploring the idea of “early warnings”, i.e. monitoring the resilience of tipping elements over the observed (or reconstructed) time period. The session focuses on limitations, uncertainties and potential solutions related to such methods, as well as methods to detect tipping events in time series, and methods to estimate the time (or parameter value) when tipping might happen in the future.

Keynote talk 1: Assessment paper on high impact climate events, tipping points and irreversible regional impacts

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Gabi Hegerl

Affiliation: University of Edinburgh

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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Abstract: This presentation will briefly outline the status of an assessment and review paper that is underway, supported by the World Climate Research Programme and aiming to begin the process of consensus building ahead of IPCC. Its scope is threshold breaching, irreversibility and tipping, and it focuses on tipping elements both global and regional, irreversibility and high impact unknown likelihood events including in impacts. The main focus of the paper is on the physical climate system, but it includes types of climate events that lead to tipping in impacts. It contains sections on definition and framing of tipping and events of concern; and evidence and mechanisms for them in ocean and cryosphere, boreal and tropical regions, tipping in impact and the ability of Earth system models to capture such events.

Keynote talk 2: Uncertainties in Tipping Warning and Prediction

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Maya Ben Yami

Affiliation: Technical University Munich

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Submission date: 7 March 2025

Abstract: Observations are increasingly used to detect critical slowing down (CSD) in potentially multistable components of the Earth system in order to warn of forthcoming critical transitions in these components. In addition, it has been suggested to use the statistical changes in these historical observations to extrapolate into the future and predict the tipping time. However, such detections and predictions are sensitive to multiple sources of uncertainties, namely: modelling assumptions, representativeness of fingerprint time series, and the inherent biases and uncertainties of the used observational datasets. Using the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) as an example, I will first present an in-depth uncertainty analysis of AMOC CSD indicators, and then analyse the effect of uncertainties on the prediction of an AMOC tipping time. Whilst signs of AMOC CSD remain significant when accounting for these uncertainties, they prove too large for a useful prediction of an AMOC tipping time from historical data.

Presentation 1: Comparing Resilience Concepts in Bifurcating Systems of Intermediate Complexity

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Andreas Morr

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Submission date: 5 March 2025

Abstract: Resilience concepts have shaped systems analysis methodology across scientific disciplines and the public sphere. Generally, "resilience" denotes an inherent quality of system stability. Depending on the application or the context, it can have different concrete definitions. In this talk, we discuss several resilience concepts based on the framework of dynamical systems theory. The associated measures of resilience are broadly separated into local and non-local measures. Local resilience comprises a system's response to small disturbances, while non-local resilience synthesizes information about the entire state space and its basins of attraction. We numerically quantify resilience for several applied dynamical systems according to local and non-local measures. We achieve this by augmenting the DynamicalSystems.jl Julia package. The added functionality allows to efficiently compute resilience measures and track their changes in response to system parameter shifts. We employ the novel numerical methodology to assess changes in system resilience in the advent of bifurcation tipping points.

Presentation 2: Cataloguing abrupt shifts in CMIP6 models: from ocean physics to biogeochemistry

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Eike Köhn

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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Authors: Joran Angevaere, Sybren Drijfhout, Eike E. Köhn, Juliette Mignot, Lester Kwiatkowski, Guillaume Gastineau

Abstract: Abrupt shifts in ocean physics and biogeochemistry, forced by anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, can profoundly change the future climate and marine ecosystem functioning. However, the potential for abrupt shifts is often overlooked in future projections, as multi-model means tend to smooth out abrupt shifts simulated by individual models. Here, we identify dramatic changes in individual models of the CMIP6 model suite, by using a newly developed automated detection algorithm. Analysing physical oceanic and atmospheric variables in all available models and five future scenarios, we detect major shifts primarily linked to sea-ice decline, North Atlantic subpolar gyre weakening, and Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) changes. Applying the algorithm to net primary productivity (NPP), initially yields no dramatic shifts within 14 analysed models. However, relaxing the employed detection criteria, which were developed for the physical variables, by 25, 50, and 60% reveals sudden and pronounced NPP declines, mostly in the North Atlantic. Initial analyses indicate that these are tied to the subpolar gyre weakening. Hence, a refined set of detection criteria can enable the identification and cataloguing of

dramatic changes in biogeochemical fields, which supports the investigation into their drivers and potential early warning indicators.

Session 5: Impacts and communication of TP results with public and media

Welcome to this session on climate tipping points impacts and communication, where we'll explore emerging scientific, societal, and financial perspectives on one of the most urgent climate challenges. We begin with a keynote from Robert Vautard, offering a timely update on the IPCC's upcoming 7th Assessment Report and the scientific hurdles ahead for Working Group I. Following this, our speakers will unpack how tipping points are communicated across sectors—from the dynamics of scientific consensus and public engagement to the practical framing of risks in the financial world, and the early findings from ongoing research into societal and ecosystem impacts. Together, these talks contribute to crucial debates on how we define, assess, and communicate tipping point risks across different audiences and disciplines.

Keynote talk: The IPCC Outlines of AR7 and challenges for WGI

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Robert Vautard
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Submission date: 8 March 2025

Abstract: This presentation will focus on the expected products of the IPCC in the 7th Assessment Cycle, and give an update of the production. In particular, the IPCC outlines of WGI-II-III reports will be presented, with an emphasis on WGI. The presentation will also highlight the main scientific challenges expected to be tackled in AR7 WGI, using illustrations from recent studies.

Presentation 1: Tipping Points in Climate Communication: Scientific Consensus, Risk Perception, and Public Engagement

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Imke Hoppe
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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Abstract: The concept of climate tipping points plays a crucial role in scientific discourse and public debate. This study aims to investigate how climate scientists assess the risks associated with tipping points, the degree of consensus within the scientific community, and the role of climate science in public and political discourse. A survey among climate scientists is planned to examine their perspectives on the likelihood, timing, and potential consequences of major tipping points, as well as their views on the effectiveness of different communication strategies.

If initial results become available, they may provide insights into the extent of scientific agreement on the urgency and potential irreversibility of tipping points, as well as variations

in preferred communication approaches. Some scientists may emphasize the necessity of strong risk-based messaging to convey urgency, while others may highlight concerns about catastrophe framing leading to public disengagement. Additionally, the survey will explore scientists' perceptions of their role in media engagement and policy advising, revealing differing attitudes toward acting as an Honest Broker versus an Epistocrat in science communication.

Presentation 2: From Data to Dollars: Making Tipping Points Tangible

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Russ Bowdrey

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Submission date: 10 March 2025

Abstract: Climate change and tipping points are obviously a pressing issue, yet its translation into the language of finance often requires a different narrative. This session explores how investors—whose decisions are ultimately driven by balance sheets, profits, and bonuses—integrate climate risk as just one factor in a broader decision matrix. Drawing on insights from a recent MSCI Survey Report, the talk will reveal that for many finance professionals, the focus isn't solely on humanity's fate but also on the immediate, tangible impacts that affect financial performance. This ultimately gives quite a nuanced framing to the way tipping point impacts apply to current decision making. Join us to discover how you can reframe your climate science communication to emphasize the near-term risks that move markets, bridging the gap between robust scientific evidence and the practical priorities of the financial world.

Presentation 3: Societal and ecosystem impacts of climate tipping points. First results from TipESM.

Submitting author/speaker (Name and Surname): Andrew Hartley

Affiliation: Met Office

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Submission date: 19 March 2025

Abstract: This talk explores the motivation behind extending the analysis of climate tipping points beyond climate variables, and the gaps in the literature on this subject. We will take a first look at results from impacts indices, and an initial analysis of the model biases in UKESM simulations. Since this work is still in its early stages, we will also present future plans and describe how impacts work will contribute towards a risk register at the end of the project.